

**PYODERMA ASSOCIATED WITH ALLERGODERMATOSIS,
ASSESSMENT OF THE QUALITY OF THERAPY**

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Abstract: *The study analyzes modern concepts of etiology, pathogenesis, and treatment of vulgar acne associated with allergic skin diseases. Particular attention was paid to the central role of local manifestations leading to the appearance of acne in a cascade of hormonal, immunological and microbiological changes. As described in the treatment of acne, evidence-based medical approaches are used to determine the most effective treatment.*

Keywords: *Allergic diseases, vulgar acne, therapy, effectiveness of treatment.*

Introduction: The incidence of allergies in the world is increasing among adults and children. According to world data, 30-50% of the population suffers from allergic diseases. In fact, this is the epidemic of the 21st century. Only in Europe more than 150 million people suffer from allergic diseases, of which half a billion - allergic rhinitis, more than 300 million - bronchial asthma. Acne vulgaris (pimples, acne) is one of the

most common diseases that affects 90-95% of the world's population. The highest incidence was registered in the period from 12 to 25 years. However, in approximately 7% of patients, late acne (adult acne) may occur after 40 years of age. Most patients with a severe course of the disease develop irreversible anti-inflammatory skin changes that require long-term and complex treatment, no less than the appearance of acne in patients. The presence of cosmetic defects negatively affects the mental and emotional state of patients, reduces self-esteem, leads to depressive disorders, leads to social disorders. In recent years, some progress has been made in the study of the pathogenesis of acne. According to modern concepts, the appearance of acne occurs against the background of interrelated pathogenetic mechanisms. The most important of them are the violation of keratinization processes, pathological follicular hyperkeratosis, lipid imbalance and hyperproduction of sebum along with the proliferation of microorganisms, among which *Propionibacterium acnes* plays a key role. In the pathogenesis of acne, immune diseases are important, characterized by the activation of cell-mediated reactions of the leukocyte system and the functional state of the humoral immunity. The development of appropriate therapy is determined by the pathogenetic mechanisms of acne and includes external and systemic drugs (antibiotics, synthetic retinoids, antiandrogenic and immunotropic agents), physiotherapy, peeling, etc. However, long-term treatment is often required, which can lead to serious side effects, complications and resistance to the drugs used. medicines. Given these problems, it seems interesting to develop an integrated approach to the treatment of the most common forms of acne using local antibacterial and anti-inflammatory drugs with specific protective mechanisms, and antidepressants that prevent the development of resistance, promote recovery with a clear vegetative stabilizing effect.

Objective: To determine the effectiveness of a complex method for the treatment of acne vulgaris associated with allergic skin diseases.

Materials and methods. To carry out our work, 52 patients with acne vulgaris were examined, who were on inpatient treatment and received outpatient treatment in

the Samarkand Regional Hospital. The mean age of the observed patients was 18.27 ± 12.6 years. 41 (73%) boys and 11 (27%) girls were examined. The duration of the disease in patients ranged from 1 to 3 years. Criteria for inclusion of patients in the observation group included: the presence of clinical evidence of acne vulgaris, the patient's informed consent to participate in the study with clinical and laboratory studies of therapy, the application of treatment recommendations

The exclusion criteria for patients from the main group were: complex forms of acne vulgaris, malignant neoplasms, chronic diseases of the internal organs of an infectious-allergic nature, a clear diagnosis of hepatitis, including an increased risk; The last treatment for acne vulgaris was less than 1 month ago, as well as a violation of the treatment regimen.

Results and discussion: All examined patients were divided into 2 groups, main and control; the main group included patients who received standard treatment for acne vulgaris.

The control group included patients who received drugs: lacto-ji 1 capsule 3 times a day for 20 days, Trikhopol 1 tablet 3 times a day for 10 days, Fukarsin for burning 1 time a day at night, before going to bed. Ointment Mupiroban 2% is rubbed for 15 days and a solution of ziniride 2 times a week.

Patients were hospitalized for 10 days, after which patients continued outpatient treatment for 1 month, with outpatient treatment, patients visited the attending physician every 10 days to evaluate the effectiveness of treatment.

To determine the effectiveness of treatment, the following criteria were used: a positive effect of therapy at the beginning of treatment, the timing of sowing bacterial pathology in the foci, the timing of clinical recovery.

In the main group, positive dynamics was noted in 4 patients on the 10th day, treatment was changed on the 5th day, positive dynamics was noted in 15 patients on the 20th day of treatment, complete clinical recovery was noted in 2 patients on the 30th day. day. treatment, positive dynamics was noted in 3 patients. 12 Clinical recovery was noted in 12 patients. On the 40th day of treatment, 16 out of 26 patients

had a complete clinical recovery, and 10 continued treatment. There were no visible changes in patients, as a result

In the control group of 26 patients, 10 patients showed positive dynamics on the 10th day, on the 20th day of treatment, positive dynamics was noted in another 20 patients, complete clinical recovery in 15 patients, after 30 days of treatment in 26 patients, complete clinical recovery in 24 patients, 2 patients continued treatment. There were no visible changes in patients, as a result

Conclusions: Thus, the proposed treatment complex turned out to be more effective in the treatment of acne vulgaris. A positive effect was observed in all 26 observed cases, while this method increased the activity of rapid recovery and reduced complications (post-acne).

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